

Lyapunov-type inequalities for fractional differential equations

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Abstract

The principal aim of this paper is to discuss Lyapunov-type inequalities for fractional differential equations with fractional boundary conditions. Some new Lyapunov's inequalities are established, which almost generalize and improve some earlier results in the literature.

Keywords: Lyapunov-type inequalities; Fractional differential equations; Riemann-Liouville derivative; Green's function; Boundary conditions.

1. Introduction

We recall the well-known Lyapunov inequality for Hill's equation

$$x''(t) + q(t)x(t) = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

where $q(t) \in L^1[a, b]$ is a real-valued function. If $x(t)$ is a nontrivial solution of Eq. (1.1) such that $x(a) = x(b) = 0$, where $a < b$ are two consecutive zeros of $x(t)$, then the following inequality holds:

$$\int_a^b |q(t)| dt > \frac{4}{b-a}, \quad (1.2)$$

where the constant 4 is sharp^[1], and Ineq. (1.2) is known as Lyapunov inequality.

The Lyapunov-type inequality and its generalizations have been used as a useful tool in oscillation theory, eigenvalue problems, disconjugacy, and many other areas of differential and difference equations, see for instance [2-5, 8-10] and the references cited therein.

The study of Lyapunov-type inequalities for fractional differential functions has begun recently. Ferreira^[7] first study Lyapunov inequality in this direction, where he derived a Lyapunov-type inequality as follows.

Theorem 1.1 (see [7]) Consider the fractional boundary value problem

$$\begin{cases} {}_a D^\alpha x(t) + q(t)x(t) = 0, a < t < b, \\ x(a) = x(b) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (1.3)$$

where ${}_a D^\alpha$ is the (left) Riemann-Liouville derivative of order $\alpha \in (1, 2]$ and $q(t) : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuous function. If Eq. (1.3) has a nontrivial solution, then

$$\int_a^b |q(s)| ds > \Gamma(\alpha) \left(\frac{4}{b-a} \right)^{\alpha-1}. \quad (1.4)$$

In 2017, Agarwall et al.^[6] studied Lyapunov type inequalities for mixed nonlinear fractional differential equations with a forcing term

$$\begin{cases} {}_a D^\alpha(x(t)) + p(t)|x(t)|^{\mu-1}x(t) + q(t)|x(t)|^{\gamma-1}x(t) = f(t), \\ x(a) = x(b) = 0, \end{cases}$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 2, 0 < \gamma < 1 < \mu < 2$.

In this paper, we obtain Lyapunov-type inequalities for the Riemann-Liouville fractional nonlinear differential equations with a forcing term

$$\begin{cases} D_{a^+}^\beta(r(t)D_{a^+}^\alpha x(t)) + \sum_{k=1}^n p_k(t)|x(t)|^{\mu_k-1}x(t) = f(t), a < t < b, \\ x(a) = x'(a) = x'(b) = 0, D_{a^+}^\alpha x(a) = D_{a^+}^\alpha x(b) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (1.5)$$

where $0 < \mu_k < 2, 1 \leq k \leq n, \alpha \in (2, 3], \beta \in (1, 2], p_k(t), f(t) : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are continuous functions for all $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$, and $r(t) \in C[a, b]$ such that $r(t) > 0$.

The organization of the rest of this paper is as follows: the next Section recalls some definitions and Lemmas which will play an important role in the proof of our main results. In Section 3, we establish some new Lyapunov-type inequalities for Eq. (1.5), and an example illustrating the result is also given in Section 4.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we introduce some preliminaries.

Definition 2.1 The Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative of order $\alpha \geq 0$ is defined by

$$(D_{a^+}^0 f)(t) = f(t)$$

and

$$(D_{a^+}^\alpha f)(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \left(\frac{d}{dt}\right)^n \int_a^t \frac{f(s)}{(t-s)^{\alpha-n+1}} ds, t \in [a, b],$$

where $n = [\alpha] + 1$.

Lemma 2.2^[6] If A is positive, and B, z are nonnegative, then

$$Az^2 - Bz^\alpha + (2-\alpha)\alpha^{\alpha/(2-\alpha)} 2^{2/(\alpha-2)} A^{-\alpha/(2-\alpha)} B^{2/(2-\alpha)} \geq 0$$

for any $\alpha \in (0, 2)$ with equality holding if and only if $B = z = 0$.

Lemma 2.3^[4] Let $\alpha > 0$, if $D_{a^+}^\alpha u \in C[a, b]$, then

$$I_{a^+}^\alpha D_{a^+}^\alpha u(t) = u(t) + \sum_{k=1}^n c_k (t-a)^{\alpha-k},$$

where $n = [\alpha] + 1$.

Lemma 2.4^[4] Let $2 < \alpha \leq 3$ and $y \in C[a, b]$. Then the problem

$$\begin{cases} D_{a^+}^\alpha u(t) + y(t) = 0, a < t < b, \\ u(a) = u'(a) = u'(b) = 0 \end{cases}$$

has a unique solution

$$u(t) = \int_a^b G(t, s)y(s)ds,$$

where

$$G(t, s) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \begin{cases} \left(\frac{b-s}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha-2} (t-a)^{\alpha-1} - (t-s)^{\alpha-1}, a \leq s \leq t \leq b, \\ \left(\frac{b-s}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha-2} (t-a)^{\alpha-1}, a \leq t \leq s \leq b. \end{cases}$$

Lemma 2.5 Let $y \in C[a, b], 1 < \beta \leq 2 < \alpha \leq 3, r(t) > 0$ and $r(t) \in C[a, b]$. Then the problem

$$\begin{cases} D_{a^+}^\beta (r(t)D_{a^+}^\alpha x(t)) + y(t) = 0, a < t < b, \\ x(a) = x'(a) = x'(b) = 0, D_{a^+}^\alpha x(a) = D_{a^+}^\alpha x(b) = 0 \end{cases}$$

has a unique solution

$$x(t) = -\int_a^b G(t,s) \left(\frac{1}{r(s)} \int_a^b H(s,\tau) y(\tau) d\tau \right) ds,$$

where

$$G(t,s) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \begin{cases} \left(\frac{b-s}{b-a} \right)^{\alpha-2} (t-a)^{\alpha-1} - (t-s)^{\alpha-1}, a \leq s \leq t \leq b, \\ \left(\frac{b-s}{b-a} \right)^{\alpha-2} (t-a)^{\alpha-1}, a \leq t \leq s \leq b, \end{cases}$$

$$H(t,s) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \begin{cases} \left(\frac{b-s}{b-a} \right)^{\beta-1} (t-a)^{\beta-1} - (t-s)^{\beta-1}, a \leq s \leq t \leq b, \\ \left(\frac{b-s}{b-a} \right)^{\beta-1} (t-a)^{\beta-1}, a \leq t \leq s \leq b. \end{cases}$$

Proof. From Lemma 2.3 we have

$$r(t)D_{a^+}^\alpha x(t) = -\int_a^t \frac{(t-s)^{\beta-1}}{\Gamma(\beta)} y(s) ds + c_1(t-a)^{\beta-1} + c_2(t-a)^{\beta-2},$$

where $c_i, i = 1, 2$, are real constants. The condition $D_{a^+}^\alpha x(a) = 0$ implies that $r(a)D_{a^+}^\alpha x(a) = 0$, which concludes $c_2 = 0$. Then the condition $D_{a^+}^\alpha x(b) = 0$ implies that $r(b)D_{a^+}^\alpha x(b) = 0$, which yields

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^b \left(\frac{b-s}{b-a} \right)^{\beta-1} y(s) ds.$$

Then

$$r(t)D_{a^+}^\alpha x(t) = -\int_a^t \frac{(t-s)^{\beta-1}}{\Gamma(\beta)} y(s) ds + \frac{(t-a)^{\beta-1}}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^b \left(\frac{b-s}{b-a} \right)^{\beta-1} y(s) ds,$$

this is,

$$r(t)D_{a^+}^\alpha x(t) = \int_a^b H(t,\tau) y(\tau) d\tau.$$

Therefore,

$$D_{a^+}^\alpha x(t) - \frac{1}{r(t)} \int_a^b H(t,\tau) y(\tau) d\tau = 0.$$

Setting

$$y_1(t) = -\frac{1}{r(t)} \int_a^b H(t,\tau) y(\tau) d\tau,$$

we have

$$\begin{cases} D_{a^+}^\alpha x(t) + y_1(t) = 0, a < t < b, \\ x(a) = x'(a) = x'(b) = 0. \end{cases}$$

Finally, applying Lemma 2.4, we obtain the desired result.

3. Main results

Our main results are the following Lyapunov-type inequalities.

Theorem 3.1 If Eq. (1.5) has a nontrivial continuous solution, then

$$\left[\int_a^b \frac{(b-s)^{\alpha-2}(s-a)}{r(s)} ds \right]^2 \int_a^b (b-s)^{\beta-1}(s-a)^{\beta-1} \sum_{k=1}^n |p_k(s)| ds \int_a^b (b-s)^{\beta-1} (s-a)^{\beta-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k |p_k(s)| + |f(s)| \right] ds > \frac{\Gamma^2(\alpha)\Gamma^2(\beta)(b-a)^{2\beta-2}}{4}, \quad (3.1)$$

where $\gamma_k = (2 - \mu_k) \mu_k^{\mu_k/(2-\mu_k)} 2^{2/(\mu_k-2)}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Proof. Let $x(t)$ be a nontrivial continuous solution, from Lemma 2.5, we have

$$x(t) = - \int_a^b G(t,s) \left(\frac{1}{r(s)} \int_a^b H(s,\tau) \left[\sum_{k=1}^n p_k(\tau) |x(\tau)|^{\mu_k-1} x(\tau) - f(\tau) \right] d\tau \right) ds.$$

Let $|x(c)| = \max_{t \in [a,b]} |x(t)|$. From [4] we have

$$0 \leq G(t,s) \leq G(b,s), (t,s) \in [a,b] \times [a,b],$$

$$0 \leq H(t,s) \leq H(s,s), (t,s) \in [a,b] \times [a,b].$$

As a consequence, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |x(c)| &= \left| - \int_a^b G(c,s) \left(\frac{1}{r(s)} \int_a^b H(s,\tau) \left[\sum_{k=1}^n p_k(\tau) |x(\tau)|^{\mu_k-1} x(\tau) - f(\tau) \right] d\tau \right) ds \right| \\ &\leq \int_a^b \frac{G(c,s)}{r(s)} \int_a^b H(s,\tau) \left[\sum_{k=1}^n |p_k(\tau)| |x(\tau)|^{\mu_k} + |f(\tau)| \right] d\tau ds \\ &\leq \int_a^b \frac{G(b,s)}{r(s)} \int_a^b H(\tau,\tau) \left[\sum_{k=1}^n |p_k(\tau)| |x(\tau)|^{\mu_k} + |f(\tau)| \right] d\tau ds \\ &= \int_a^b \frac{G(b,s)}{r(s)} ds \int_a^b H(s,s) \left[\sum_{k=1}^n |p_k(s)| |x(s)|^{\mu_k} + |f(s)| \right] ds \\ &\leq \sum_{k=1}^n Q_k |x(c)|^{\mu_k} + F, \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

where

$$Q_k = \int_a^b \frac{G(b,s)}{r(s)} ds \int_a^b H(s,s) |p_k(s)| ds, k = 1, 2, \dots, n,$$

$$F = \int_a^b \frac{G(b,s)}{r(s)} ds \int_a^b H(s,s) |f(s)| ds.$$

In Lemma 2.2 with $A = B = 1$, implies that

$$|x(c)|^{\mu_k} < |x(c)|^2 + \gamma_k, k = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

Using this inequality and Ineq. (3.2) we find the following quadratic inequality:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n Q_k |x(c)|^2 - |x(c)| + \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k Q_k + F > 0.$$

But this is only possible when

$$\sum_{k=1}^n Q_k (\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k Q_k + F) > \frac{1}{4},$$

which is the same as (3.1). This completes the proof of Theorem 3.1.

Theorem 3.2 If Eq. (1.5) has a nontrivial continuous solution, then

$$\left[\int_a^b \frac{(b-s)^{\alpha-2}(s-a)}{r(s)} ds \right]^2 \int_a^b \sum_{k=1}^n |p_k(s)| ds \int_a^b \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k |p_k(s)| + |f(s)| \right] ds > \frac{4^{2\beta-3} \Gamma^2(\alpha) \Gamma^2(\beta)}{(b-a)^{2\beta-2}}, \quad (3.3)$$

where $\gamma_k = (2 - \mu_k) \mu_k^{\mu_k/(2-\mu_k)} 2^{2/(\mu_k-2)}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Proof. Let $\psi(s) = (b-s)(s-a)$, $s \in [a, b]$. Observe that the function $\psi(s)$ has a maximum at the point

$s_1 = \frac{a+b}{2}$, that is,

$$\psi_{\max}(s) = \psi(s_1) = \frac{(b-a)^2}{4}.$$

The desired result follows immediately from the last equality and inequality (3.1). This completes the proof of Theorem 3.2.

Theorem 3.3 If Eq. (1.5) has a nontrivial continuous solution, then

$$\left(\int_a^b \frac{ds}{r(s)} \right)^2 \int_a^b \sum_{k=1}^n |p_k(s)| ds \int_a^b \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k |p_k(s)| + |f(s)| \right] ds > \frac{4^{2\beta-3} \Gamma^2(\alpha) \Gamma^2(\beta) (\alpha-1)^{2\alpha-2}}{(\alpha-2)^{2\alpha-4} (b-a)^{2(\alpha+\beta-2)}}, \quad (3.4)$$

where $\gamma_k = (2 - \mu_k) \mu_k^{\mu_k/(2-\mu_k)} 2^{2/(\mu_k-2)}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Proof. Let

$$\phi(s) = (b-s)^{\alpha-2}(s-a), s \in [a, b],$$

then

$$\phi'(s) = (b-s)^{\alpha-3}[b-s-(\alpha-2)(s-a)], s \in [a, b].$$

When $s_* = \frac{b+a(\alpha-2)}{\alpha-1}$, the function has $\phi'(s_*) = 0$. So the function $\phi(s)$ has a maximum at the point

$s_* = \frac{b+a(\alpha-2)}{\alpha-1}$, this is

$$\phi_{\max}(s) = \phi(s_*) = (\alpha-2)^{\alpha-2} \left(\frac{b-a}{\alpha-1} \right)^{\alpha-1}.$$

The desired result follows immediately from the last equality and inequality (3.3). This completes the proof of Theorem 3.3.

For $\alpha = 3, \beta = 2$, Eq. (1.5) becomes

$$\begin{cases} (r(t)x^{(3)}(t))^n + \sum_{k=1}^n p_k(t)|x(t)|^{\mu_k-1} x(t) = f(t), a < t < b, \\ x(a) = x'(a) = x'(b) = 0, x^{(3)}(a) = x^{(3)}(b) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

In this case, taking $\alpha = 3, \beta = 2$ in Theorem 3.1, we obtain the following result.

Corollary 3.4 If Eq. (3.5) has a nontrivial continuous solution, then

$$\left(\int_a^b \frac{(b-s)(s-a)}{r(s)} ds\right)^2 \int_a^b (b-s)(s-a) \sum_{k=1}^n |p_k(s)| ds \int_a^b (b-s)(s-a) \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k |p_k(s)| + |f(s)|\right] ds > (b-a)^2, \quad (3.6)$$

where $\gamma_k = (2 - \mu_k) \mu_k^{\mu_k/(2-\mu_k)} 2^{2/(\mu_k-2)}, k = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Corollary 3.5 If Eq. (3.5) has a nontrivial continuous solution, then

$$\left(\int_a^b \frac{ds}{r(s)}\right)^2 \int_a^b \sum_{k=1}^n |p_k(s)| ds \int_a^b \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k |p_k(s)| + |f(s)|\right] ds > \frac{256}{(b-a)^6}, \quad (3.7)$$

where $\gamma_k = (2 - \mu_k) \mu_k^{\mu_k/(2-\mu_k)} 2^{2/(\mu_k-2)}, k = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

4. Example

Example 4.1 Consider the fractional equation

$$\begin{cases} D_{0^+}^{\frac{5}{3}}(D_{0^+}^{\frac{7}{3}}x(t)) + p_1(t)|x(t)|^{-\frac{1}{3}}x(t) + p_2(t)|x(t)|^{\frac{1}{3}}x(t) = f(t), t \geq 0, \\ x(0) = x'(0) = x'(b) = 0, D_{0^+}^{\frac{7}{3}}x(0) = D_{0^+}^{\frac{7}{3}}x(b) = 0, \end{cases}$$

where $p_1(t), p_2(t)$ and $f(t) : [0, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are continuous functions. If the solution $x(t)$ has consecutive zeros at 0 and $b > 0$, in view of Theorem 3.1 the following inequality must be satisfied

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\int_0^b (b-s)^{\frac{1}{3}} s ds\right]^2 \int_0^b (b-s)^{\frac{2}{3}} s^{\frac{2}{3}} (|p_1(s)| + |p_2(s)|) ds \int_0^b (b-s)^{\frac{2}{3}} s^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(2 \times \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{\frac{2}{3}} |p_1(s)| \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{4}{27} |p_2(s)| + |f(s)|\right) ds > \frac{\Gamma^2\left(\frac{7}{3}\right)\Gamma^2\left(\frac{5}{3}\right)b^{\frac{4}{3}}}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

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